

ARISE

Assistive Technology in Inclusive and Resilient Systems and Enabling Environments

Policy Framework and Evaluative Tool

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Background

Assistive technology is fundamental to achieving inclusion and enabling persons with functional limitations to exercise their human rights across all life domains, including education, employment, health, social participation, civic engagement, and independent living. The United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (UNCRPD), ratified by 191 countries, establishes AT as integral to multiple rights including personal mobility (Article 20), living independently and being included in the community (Article 19), education (Article 24), and work and employment (Article 27) (United Nations, 2006).(1) AT access also contributes to achieving Sustainable Development Goals including health and well-being (SDG 3), quality education (SDG 4), decent work (SDG 8), reduced inequalities (SDG 10), and sustainable cities (SDG 11).(2) Furthermore, the realization of all rights encoded in the UNCRPD, as well as the achievement of the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) have also been clearly linked through research evidence to the provision of assistive technology.(3,4) Despite this rights-based framework, an estimated 2.5 billion people globally need AT, yet only 10% have access, with particularly acute gaps in lower resourced contexts and among marginalized populations.(5) This gap is less acute, but still very present in higher resourced contexts, where a substantial number of people have unmet needs, including needs which have not been met with appropriate assistive technology.

Assistive technology (AT) is defined by the World Health Organization as "the application of organized knowledge and skills related to assistive products, including systems and services".(6) An assistive product (AP) is "any external product, especially produced or generally available, the primary purpose of which is to maintain or improve an individual's functioning and independence, and thereby promote their well-being".(6) Appropriate assistive technology refers to AT that meets the user's needs and environmental conditions, provides proper fit and postural support, is safe and durable, is available in the country, and can be obtained, maintained, and serviced at an affordable cost.(7)

Global and regional policy drivers increasingly recognize AT access as essential. The World Health Assembly Resolution 71.8 (2018) called on member states to scale up access to AT through national strategies, workforce development, financing mechanisms, and integration within universal health coverage.(8) WHO initiatives including the Priority Assistive Products List, the Global Cooperation on Assistive Technology (GATE) programme, and the 2022 Global Report on Assistive Technology provide technical guidance and frameworks for national action.(5,6) Regional instruments including the European Accessibility Act and the Strategy for the Rights of Persons with Disabilities 2021-2030 establish accessibility standards and AT provision requirements.(9,10)

Despite this policy momentum, significant challenges persist in the current AT policy landscape. Research and policy reviews identify interconnected barriers spanning conceptual fragmentation (varying definitions and scope of AT across sectors), regulatory barriers (overly restrictive standards stifling innovation or delaying access), service delivery challenges (lack of person-centered assessment, fragmented provision pathways, inadequate follow-up), insufficient and inflexible financing, critical workforce shortages and training gaps, poor coordination across health, education, social protection and other sectors, and limited cultural competency and attention to intersectionality in AT provision.(5,11) Existing AT policy frameworks often address components in isolation rather than taking comprehensive, systems-oriented approaches, and frequently lack attention to resilience, or the capacity of AT systems to maintain essential functions during crises, emergencies, and humanitarian situations.(12,13)

Methodology

The development of the **ARISE Framework for Resilient and Inclusive Assistive Technology (AT) Systems** followed a participatory, multi-phase process integrating evidence synthesis, expert consensus, and real-world validation. The methodology ensured that the framework is grounded in global best practices, informed by lived experience, and adaptable across diverse economic and policy contexts. The methodology was underpinned by the principles of the United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (UNCRPD) and participatory research ethics. The process centred the perspectives of persons with disabilities and other AT users through an advisory group and by ensuring the participation of assistive technology users in all stages of the development, ensuring that the framework reflects real-world priorities and rights-based approaches to AT provision.

Phase 1: Systematic Review of AT Policies and Systems

The first phase involved a scoping review to identify research in the area of assistive technology policy, as well as existing assistive technology policies, and policies relevant to assistive technology currently in force throughout Europe (including countries belonging to the EU, EEA, and UK). Using Arksey and O'Malley's (2005) five-step methodological framework, the review included comprehensive searches across academic databases and grey literature, including policy reports, WHO publications, and national AT strategies and policy documents.(14) Data were extracted on key principles and features of assistive technology policy, including recommendations for policy. This phase established the evidence base and conceptual foundations for subsequent framework development, and to feed into the participatory consensus-based process.

Phase 2: Participatory Consensus Process

In the second phase, a participatory consensus-based process was conducted to identify key concepts that promote inclusion and resilience in AT systems. The consensus process engaged a diverse group of stakeholders from 16 countries in Europe, including:

- AT users and representatives of organizations of AT users;
- Policymakers and service providers; and
- Researchers and practitioners with demonstrated leadership in AT system design.

The process was based on a methodology of consensus building used previously in assistive technology research and included two consensus-based meetings with group discussion, with a survey between to establish agreement on concepts of interest.(15,16) International sign language interpretation and captioning were provided throughout. This participatory approach ensured that insights were co-produced with people with lived experience and experts from across Europe.

Phase 3: Framework Development, Piloting, and Refinement

Drawing on the findings from Phases 1 and 2, a draft ARISE Framework was developed outlining the key components of resilient and inclusive AT systems. The framework includes:

- Principles underpinning inclusive and resilient assistive technology policies;
- A policy framework laying out core features of inclusive and resilient assistive technology policies; and

- A draft evaluative tool with key questions addressing the principles and features of existing policies, including instructions for use.

The draft framework was piloted in five countries with differing economic profiles and existing AT commitments. Each pilot involved:

- A review of the ARISE Framework to provide targeted feedback; and
- A policy review using the draft ARISE evaluative tool; and
- Focus groups to evaluate applicability, strengths, and areas for improvement.

Findings from the pilots were used to refine the framework, ensuring that it is relevant and context-sensitive across European contexts.

The ARISE framework was developed through consultation with experts primarily from the European region and may require contextual adaptation for low-resource settings or specific national contexts. Evidence gaps exist in certain areas, particularly regarding assistive technology provision in humanitarian settings and the effectiveness of different financing models. The framework is not prescriptive and cannot replace localized policy development, stakeholder engagement, or rigorous impact evaluation of implemented policies. Ongoing research and periodic revision will strengthen its evidence base.

How This Framework Can be Used

How is Policy Defined?

There is no single definition of policy, and what constitutes policy in a certain context may differ from other contexts. The ARISE Framework is designed to apply to a *policy ecosystem* which may include written legislation, published and unpublished policy programmes and schemes, formal guidance, and organizational policies. For the purposes of this document, the term policy will be used to encompass all of these types of documents or approaches, recognizing that individual documents are unlikely to address the breadth of activity within a broader policy ecosystem.

It is important to distinguish between policy content, or that which is written and formally adopted; policy implementation, or how the policies are enacted; and service provision, which is the fundamental driver of the user experience. ARISE focuses primarily on policy content, as written in policies and systems governing the provision of assistive technology. Furthermore, ARISE is intended to be used in a national context, although in countries with federated governing systems, or significant local control over assistive technology provision, this may differ.

Who can use this framework and evaluative tool, in which contexts?

The ARISE Framework and Evaluative Tool are designed as practical tools adaptable to multiple stakeholder needs and contexts, which provide multiple entry points for different users to strengthen AT policy and practice. ARISE is meant to be used as a snapshot, rather than a full and complete evaluation of a national system of provision, which may be better served by other tools (e.g., WHO rapid Assistive Technology Assessment – rATA, and the WHO Assistive Technology Capacity Assessment – ATA-C). This allows for rapid evaluation of a national approach to assistive technology provision which can be used as a baseline for comparative analysis, or as a starting point for policy revision or development. Specific approaches which can be taken by key stakeholder groups are listed below.

Policymakers can use this framework to guide development of new national or regional assistive technology policies, to evaluate existing policies against best practice standards, or to identify gaps and areas for strengthening within current policy landscapes. The framework provides evidence-based guidance on essential policy components while remaining flexible enough to accommodate diverse governance structures, and socioeconomic contexts. Policy makers can conduct self-assessments using the Evaluative Tool to understand current policy maturity across domains, identify quick wins and foundational changes needed, and understand areas where further evaluation may be required.

Advocates and organizations of assistive technology users can use the framework as an advocacy tool to assess whether existing policies meet international standards and human rights obligations, to identify priority areas for policy reform, and to engage in dialogue with policymakers. The evaluative tool component enables advocates to document gaps and make evidence-based cases for change, conducting independent policy assessments to document gaps, make evidence-based arguments for policy reform, and engage constructively with government on policy priorities. The Evaluative Tool, paired with the Framework, enables advocacy organizations to move from general advocacy to specific, concrete policy recommendations grounded in the framework. Advocacy organizations can use evaluation results to secure donor or international support for policy advocacy, and to hold governments accountable to UNCRPD obligations.

Researchers can use the Evaluative Tool to guide comparative policy research across countries, to identify evidence gaps and research priorities, or to evaluate changes in policies within a single country. The framework provides a structured approach to understanding complex assistive technology systems and their policy considerations.

Service providers and assistive technology professionals can use the framework to understand how their work fits within broader policy contexts, to advocate within their organizations for practices aligned with policy best practices such as person-centered assessment and user participation, and to ensure their service delivery models support policy objectives.

Educators and students may use the framework in workshops or teaching as a structured discussion framework around which to discuss a policy ecosystem.

All stakeholders are encouraged to use the participatory approach outlined in the framework's methodology, through meaningful engagement with assistive technology users throughout any application of the framework, recognizing that those with lived experience of assistive technology needs are essential partners in policy development, evaluation, and implementation.

The ARISE Framework

Objectives of Inclusive and Resilient Assistive Technology Policy

Inclusive assistive technology policy ensures equitable access to appropriate, affordable, and quality AT for all people who need them, regardless of ability, age, geography, gender, ethnicity, or other intersecting identities. Inclusivity encompasses person-centered provision across health, education, employment, and social sectors, with meaningful participation of users and organizations of persons with disabilities in all policy stages.

Resilient AT policy establishes systems capable of withstanding and adapting to challenging circumstances in the jurisdiction where the policy is enacted, including economic crises, pandemics, armed conflict, natural disasters, or other disruptions. Resilience must consider measures to ensure continuity of service provision during a crisis or other challenge, which requires governments to consider potential disruptions to supply chains, the need to support workforce adaptation, fostering innovation, and building flexibility into policies so systems can respond to diverse and changing contexts.

Together, **inclusive and resilient AT policy** creates systems and enabling environments where access to assistive technology is understood fundamental human right and practical empowerment tool, enabling all people requiring AT to participate fully in all aspects of daily life.

The primary objective of inclusive and resilient AT policy is to establish comprehensive, integrated systems that guarantee timely access to appropriate assistive technology as a human right while building the flexibility and capacity necessary for systems to serve all current and potential future users equitably across diverse and changing contexts.

Key Principles of Inclusive and Resilient Assistive Technology Policy

Four key principles were identified which should be addressed within an inclusive and resilient assistive technology policy. Each of these principles is described below, with practical considerations for how these principles may be operationalized within a specific policy. It is noted that while these concepts are presented individually, there is some degree of overlap between these principles.

Rights-Based

Access to assistive technology is a fundamental human right, and a pathway to the realization of human rights. Policies should be grounded in a rights-based approach, which ensures equitable access to assistive products and related service on the basis of need, to ensure full participation in society. Policies which are framed within a rights-based approach must ensure **universality of access**, with considerations for affordability and accessibility, ensuring assistive technology reaches all who need it; **equity and non-discrimination**, addressing intersecting barriers to access including gender, age, and socioeconomic status; and **ethical considerations**, ensuring policies respect dignity, autonomy, and informed choice.

Participatory

Assistive technology users must be meaningfully engaged at all levels of policy development, implementation, and evaluation, through elements of **co-design** and **shared decision-making** authority. This engagement should be reflected through **participatory processes** which demonstrate the active

involvement of assistive technology users and relevant organizations in governance and policy decisions. Further, policies should reflect a **user-centred approach**, where policies and services are designed with and for assistive technology users, and **adapt** to diverse user needs, preferences, and contexts, rather than one-size fits all solutions. Policies and systems should enable **meaningful participation**, including removing barriers to participation.

Sustainable

Sustainable assistive technology policies aim to build **integrated** and coherent assistive technology systems which can withstand changing economic circumstances, with efficient **coordination** across sectors and institutions. Achieving sustainable policy requires a **systems-thinking** approach, which considers the development of viable markets, services, and financial models which are resilient and adaptable through national and international political change. A sustainable approach will include elements of organizational **efficiency**, with streamlined processes and resource allocation which minimizes unnecessary cost and maximizes potential impact. Finally, sustainable approaches must consider principles of **circularity**, addressing both cost-containment and environmental impact.

Innovative

Innovation in assistive technology policy extends beyond innovation of products to innovation at all levels of service delivery. Innovation should address needs for building both **human and institutional capacity** needed to delivery high quality assistive technology services, while promoting innovation and adoption of **emerging technologies**. Innovations may be seen across the areas of workforce development, including training and professional development across **diverse personnel roles** (clinical and non-clinical) across all sectors; **capacity building** for all stakeholders, including assistive technology users, families, educators, employers, and policy makers; **technology advancement** through regulatory and policy environments that support timely adoption of innovative solutions while maintaining **safety and quality standards**; and the **generation of evidence** through research, data collection, monitoring and evaluation to inform continuous improvement.

Policy Framework

The concepts which follow represent a framework of 11 components and related subcomponents which should be present in an inclusive and resilient assistive technology policy which aligns with the key principles outlined above. The inclusion of these components is considered aspirational, representing an ideal which we may strive to achieve to meet our commitments to the principles of human rights and sustainable development agreed by the majority of countries, including all countries in Europe. It is not anticipated that there are single policies which will address all components thoroughly. However, based on existing evidence, including research evidence and the opinions of experts in the field, each of these components and their respective subcomponents were deemed important to ensuring comprehensive inclusive and resilient AT policies.

Conceptualization

Policies should clearly and comprehensively define assistive technology, to ensure clarity regarding what is and what is not considered within the policy. Two internationally accepted definitions are shown in Box 1, which provide clarity and alignment with a current understanding of the scope of assistive

technology, and may be adopted by governments in lieu of an existing or outdated definition in existing policy.

Box 1. Definitions of Assistive Technology

World Health Organization

Assistive Technology is “the application of organized knowledge and skills related to assistive products, including systems and services”.(6)

An **assistive product** is “any external product (including devices, equipment, instruments or software), especially produced or generally available, the primary purpose of which is to maintain or improve an individual’s functioning and independence, and thereby promote their well-being”.(6)

International Standards Organization (ISO 9999)

An **assistive product** is a "product that optimizes a person’s functioning and reduces disability", noting that “assistive products include devices, instruments, equipment and software,” and “assistive products can be especially produced or generally available items”.(17)

In conceptualizing assistive technology, policies may wish to distinguish between assistive products and the broader category medical products. In this way, policies may acknowledge that while assistive products may in some circumstances be considered medical products, the use of assistive products extends beyond the health sector and addresses a common challenge in the medicalization of assistive technology use. This clarification may have further regulatory implications and is therefore important to identify.

Furthermore, this clarification provides an opportunity for recognition that assistive technology spans multiple domains, including health, education, social protection, employment, transportation, and housing, with outcomes measured across sectors.

Finally, definitions of assistive technology should be flexible enough to support the inclusion of emerging technologies (including mainstream consumer products used as assistive products), and products not yet available or even considered, with a focus on the purpose of use of the product, rather than strict definitions of the products themselves. This enhances long-term applicability and resilience of the policy and ensures access to novel products is not hindered by limitations in the existing frameworks.

Governance and Leadership

Governance and leadership are complex, particularly where there are multiple entities within a country with shared responsibility for the delivery of assistive technology. Regardless of the entity responsible for the policy, and even in circumstances where a policy may speak only to one sector, rather than a cross-sectoral approach, policies should clearly lay out a coordinated governance structure and approach, with consideration for shared responsibility where appropriate. In inclusive and resilient policy, the following should be addressed:

National Strategy and Policy Framework

A comprehensive, written national assistive technology strategy and policy should be developed which articulates the government's long-term vision, commitment, and priorities for AT provision. The strategy should define clear objectives, identify responsible ministries, departments, or agencies, establish timelines for implementation, and specify resource allocation mechanisms to operationalize the policy and establish targets for monitoring and evaluation. To ensure inclusion and resiliency, the strategy should be grounded in evidence and informed through meaningful stakeholder consultation, with specific mechanisms to review and update it regularly based on implementation experience and emerging needs.

Coordination Structures

Effective assistive technology systems require formalized cross-sectoral coordination mechanisms that integrate health, education, social protection, employment, transportation, housing, justice, information and communication, disaster risk reduction and humanitarian services, and other relevant sectors. Coordination structures should establish clear lines of accountability, mechanisms for information-sharing and liaison across ministries, and mechanisms to align policies and financing across sectors to eliminate duplication and gaps. Poorly coordinated systems result in confusion, increased costs, inequitable access, and failure of AT users, particularly during critical transitions between life stages and service systems. In circumstances where policies are unique to a specific sector, mechanisms should be in place to ensure coordination with other sectoral policies and systems.

Stakeholder Engagement Mechanisms

Inclusive policies should establish formalized, ongoing mechanisms for meaningful participation of assistive technology users and user organizations, industry and service providers, and other key stakeholders throughout policy implementation, monitoring, and evaluation. Effective engagement requires structured mechanisms for participation, resource allocation for stakeholder involvement, and a commitment to moving beyond consultation to genuine shared decision-making with power-sharing between traditional policy-makers and end-users.

Legislative and Regulatory Framework

Clear legislation should establish AT access as a legal right grounded in the UNCRPD's general obligations (Article 4) and specific rights (Articles 19, 20, 24, 27, 29), providing statutory basis and legal accountability for AT provision. Legislation should define eligible populations, specify entitlements and service standards, establish mechanisms for dispute resolution and accountability, and provide protection from discrimination to ensure rights are enforceable and policies are resilient to political change. In some contexts, rights may be implicit in constitutional or general human rights frameworks, and may not be stated explicitly in AT policy documents. The entirety of the rights-based framework within the country should be considered.

Data and Information Systems

Policies should establish systems for systematic collection, management, analysis, and use of AT data at the population level to inform policy decisions and monitor progress. Data systems should measure population met and unmet need, capacity to meet demand, financing, workforce availability, and the impact of AT on user outcomes, with mandatory, standardized data collection mechanisms that support evidence-based policy evolution.

Service Delivery

Policies should clearly reflect a commitment to a clearly articulated, evidence-based service delivery model that comprehensively addresses the entire AT access pathway and lifecycle. The World Health Organization's four-step process for assistive technology provision (select, fit, train/use, and follow-up) provides a foundation for understanding the essential components of quality service delivery.(7) Within this framework, policies should clearly specify how the following elements are organized and resourced:

Assessment Processes

Policies should establish that assessment must be comprehensive, person-centered, and intersectional, evaluating the individual's functioning needs, personal goals and preferences, environmental context (home, school, workplace, community), social supports, and capacity to use and maintain the technology. Assessment processes must be timely, conducted sufficiently early to prevent missed developmental windows, lost opportunities for participation, or secondary complications associated with delays in AT provision, and must accommodate the reality that AT needs change across the lifespan and in response to changing life circumstances. Assessment should involve the individual and their family or support persons as equal partners, and should be conducted by appropriately trained, multidisciplinary teams rather than relying on single professional perspectives. Policies should specify that no AT user should be denied assessment based on age, ability, geographic location, or economic status.

Provision Models

Diverse provision models may be available within a single system to accommodate different user preferences, contexts, and organizational capacities and are therefore not prescribed here. These may include direct public provision (government procures and distributes AT products), subsidized private purchase (government funds AT but users select from private suppliers), voucher or self-directed funding schemes (funds go directly to users or families to purchase AT of their choice), managed equipment stores or resource centers that loan or provide temporary AT, and hybrid models combining elements of several approaches. Policies should specify which models are available, for which products or populations, and establish standards for equity to ensure that the provision model does not constitute a barrier to access. Systems should be flexible enough to allow individual users to choose among available products where feasible, and to shift between products as their circumstances change.

User Training and Support

Service provision models should include commitments to user training provided at the time of AT delivery, tailored to the individual's learning style and literacy level, and sufficient for basic competent use. Training should address not only technical operation but also incorporation of the AT into daily activities and routines. Ongoing support should be available as users gain experience, encounter new situations requiring AT use, or experience changes in function. Training should extend beyond the AT user to family members, caregivers, educators, employers, or others in the user's support network who facilitate AT use. Policies should specify responsibility for providing training (professional staff, trained community members, peer supporters, or combinations thereof), frequency and duration of training support, and how training is accessed across diverse geographic and economic contexts.

Repair, Maintenance, and Follow-Up

Policies should outline provisions to support routine maintenance, repair of broken or worn components, and provision of replacement parts. Maintenance and repair services must be accessible locally or through established mechanisms ensuring users are not left without AT for extended periods. Policies should specify the frequency of follow-up contacts, mechanisms for identifying when AT is no longer meeting needs (due to product malfunction, changed user needs, or environmental changes), and processes for problem-solving and adjustment. Follow-up should include user satisfaction assessment and mechanisms to escalate issues preventing AT use. Funding for maintenance, repair, and follow-up should be explicitly provided within AT budgets.

Transitions and Continuity

Assistive technology users experience transitions across multiple dimensions: developmental transitions (childhood to adolescence to adulthood to older age), institutional transitions (leaving school, entering employment, moving to different housing or care settings), changes in function or ability, and geographic transitions (rural to urban movement, migration, displacement). Policies should identify key transition points in the life course and establish protocols ensuring continuity of appropriate AT provision through transitions. This includes mechanisms for communication across organizations and sectors, procedures for transferring AT information and records, pathways for reassessment following transitions, and clarity on equipment ownership and what happens to AT products when individuals transition between systems. Systems should address cross-border transitions where relevant (e.g., refugee or internally displaced populations).

Eligibility Criteria

Policies should establish eligibility frameworks grounded in human rights principles which are explicitly non-discriminatory. Eligibility should be based on individual need (presence of functioning limitation in activities relevant to the person's age and life roles) rather than diagnostic categories, avoiding situations where some groups of individuals are funded while others are not. Eligibility should not be restricted by age, economic status, employment status, residential setting, or other characteristics that would systematically exclude population groups. Eligibility criteria should be clearly published, consistently applied, and subject to appeal mechanisms ensuring fairness and preventing arbitrary denial of access. Policies should address the reality that some individuals have complex, multifaceted needs requiring AT products and services that span multiple sectors (e.g., a child requiring AT for mobility, communication, and education participation); eligibility frameworks should not fragment responsibility across sectors in ways that leave individuals with unmet needs. Policies should specify whether eligibility is based on universal rights (everyone can access) or targeted to priority populations, and if targeted, should clearly justify the rationale for targeting and establish plans to expand access over time.

Financing and Affordability

Sustainable, equitable assistive technology systems require explicit, dedicated financing mechanisms that ensure affordability for all users regardless of economic status. Financial barriers represent one of the most significant obstacles to AT access globally (5), yet many policies address financing only tangentially or fail to adequately fund the full scope of AT services. Policies should clearly specify how AT is financed and resourced across all of the following dimensions:

Funding Allocation and Budgets

National and subnational governments should establish dedicated, identifiable budget lines for assistive technology within health, education, social protection, or other relevant sector budgets. AT-specific budget allocations ensure that AT is understood to be an essential service with defined resource commitments. Budgets should be established at national and subnational levels with clarity regarding which level bears responsibility for different types of AT or populations. Budgets should be protected and sustained across political cycles to prevent provision disruptions when political priorities shift. Budgeting should be informed by need assessments and cost analysis to establish realistic, adequate allocation levels rather than arbitrary funding amounts unrelated to actual need or capacity requirements.

Funding Scope

Policies must explicitly clarify what AT-related costs are covered by public or insurance funding. Comprehensive funding should encompass not only assistive product acquisition but also assessment, fitting, user training, technical support, repairs, maintenance, replacement parts, and ongoing follow-up services throughout the product lifecycle. Many systems fund only initial product provision, leaving users to bear costs for repairs, replacements, or necessary adjustments, creating inequitable access. Funding scope should address consumable supplies (batteries, replacement components, etc.), not only durable equipment and subscription-based services for digital products. Policies should specify whether funding covers multiple AT products for individuals with multiple functioning needs, and how funding limits (if any) are determined and communicated to users and providers.

Funding Models

Multiple funding mechanisms may operate within a single country, serving different populations or AT types. These should be clearly articulated within the policy, with clear lines of responsibility for cost coverage for AT. **Insurance and reimbursement schemes** may include public health insurance that covers AT as part of universal health coverage, mandatory disability or social insurance schemes that fund AT, or voluntary private insurance options. Reimbursement mechanisms should be transparent, timely, and should not create barriers through complex paperwork or lengthy approval processes. **Co-payment and out-of-pocket cost strategies** should ensure that user affordability is prioritized: out-of-pocket costs should be minimal or eliminated entirely for those with limited economic means, as co-payments create barriers to access for populations with resource limitations. Policies may employ sliding-scale co-payments based on ability to pay, elimination of co-payments for priority populations or essential AT products, or safety-net protections preventing catastrophic out-of-pocket expenditures. Direct provision models where government directly furnishes AT products eliminate out-of-pocket costs but require substantial government investment and capacity.

Taxation Policies

Policies should consider exempting AT products from VAT or import duties to reduce prices and improve affordability, or alternatively, using tax revenues to fund AT provision for those unable to pay. Tax exemptions or deductions for AT donations by industry, tax incentives for domestic AT manufacturing, or tax policies supporting innovation in AT may strengthen market development and affordability.

Procurement Mechanisms

Government procurement of AT products significantly influences product availability, pricing, and market dynamics.(18) In many cases, government procurement mechanisms will not be outlined in an assistive

technology policy, but rather separately, through a whole of government approach to procurement. However, ideally, assistive technology policies will note the unique needs for assistive technology procurement, notably the need to maintain flexibility to accommodate diverse user needs and preferences rather than imposing standardized products on all users, balancing cost-effectiveness (obtaining best value for public resources) with user choice (avoiding situations where only the cheapest product option is funded, regardless of appropriateness for individual users), and addressing potential for ethical concerns relating to fair pricing, conflict of interest, or product monopolies.

Assistive Technology Workforce

Assistive technology service delivery depends fundamentally on an adequate, trained, competent workforce capable of providing quality AT services across sectors and geographic regions. Policies should address the following dimensions:

Provider Roles and Competencies

Assistive technology provision requires diverse competencies. Policies should recognize and define a range of provider roles depending on the context which may include traditional rehabilitation professionals; AT technicians and technical specialists with expertise in device fitting, adaptation, and troubleshooting; AT counselors or advisors supporting user decision-making; peer supporters with lived experience of AT use; community health workers trained in basic AT provision; educators integrating AT into educational settings; employment specialists supporting AT in workplace contexts; and administrative staff managing AT programs.

Competency frameworks should specify the knowledge, skills, and attitudes required for different roles, recognizing that competent AT provision can be delivered by individuals with diverse educational backgrounds. Competency frameworks may be used to guide workforce development through pre-service training and continuing professional development.(19)

Policies should establish mechanisms for recognizing and credentialing assistive technology competencies, in both professional qualifications and other workforce cadres, enabling individuals with strong practical expertise or lived experience to contribute to the AT workforce.

Workforce Planning

Policies should establish mechanisms for workforce planning which establish targets for workforce size and composition needed to meet population AT needs, informed by need assessment and modeling of service demand. Planning should identify priority areas for workforce expansion (e.g., rural regions, specific populations, emerging AT domains). Training and employment incentives may be needed to attract workforce to underserved areas or specialties. Workforce planning should address retention, as high turnover in AT roles reduces capacity and increases training costs; retention strategies may include career advancement pathways, continuing education support, and adequate compensation. Planning should include domestic production of AT professionals where possible.

Standards and Quality Assurance

Quality and safety are fundamental to appropriate assistive technology provision, yet overly restrictive regulatory frameworks can delay access to beneficial products and stifle innovation. Policies must establish clear quality and safety standards that protect users while remaining proportionate to actual risks and avoiding unnecessary barriers to market entry or product access. Standards should be

established through transparent, evidence-based processes with input from users, providers, manufacturers, and regulatory experts.

Standards and Quality Assurance

Minimum quality standards should define acceptable performance, durability, usability, and reliability for AT products. Quality standards should be specific to AT product categories (wheelchairs, hearing aids, communication devices, etc.), recognizing that different product types have different quality requirements and failure modes. Standards should address not only physical product quality but also user-relevant factors such as ease of use, customizability to individual needs, availability of spare parts, and longevity. Standards should be informed by international standards where these exist (such as International Organization for Standardization standards) while allowing flexibility for local contexts and resource constraints. Quality assurance mechanisms should include pre-market evaluation ensuring products meet standards before distribution, post-market surveillance to identify safety issues and product failures, and mechanisms for product recall if serious problems emerge. Importantly, quality standards should not be so stringent or expensive to meet that they prevent small manufacturers, local producers, or innovation in resource-limited settings. User feedback and adverse event reporting should be integrated into ongoing quality assurance.

Safety Standards

Device safety standards should address foreseeable risks of harm and should require manufacturers to design products to mitigate these risks. Safety standards should specify testing methodologies, documentation requirements, and labeling/instruction requirements enabling users to understand safe use, which may align with international testing standards. Emergency protocols should exist for rapid safety alerts and product removal if serious safety issues are identified. Standards should be evidence-based and regularly reviewed to ensure they reflect current understanding of actual risks.

Interoperability and Compatibility Standards

Many AT users require multiple, complementary devices working together seamlessly (e.g., hearing aid compatible with mobile devices, communication device interfacing with computer systems, environmental controls integrating with smart home technology). Policies should promote interoperability standards ensuring that AT products from different manufacturers can function together and that AT works across multiple platforms and systems. Interoperability standards may include technical specifications for data formats, communication protocols, and connectivity requirements. Standards should be developed through inclusive, transparent processes with participation by assistive technology users.

Innovation, Research and Development

Assistive technology innovation is essential to meet evolving user needs, leverage new technologies, and improve cost-effectiveness and accessibility. The policy environment significantly influences whether innovation translates into improved AT access or remains confined to out of pocket payors. Policies should create environments fostering responsible innovation while ensuring that innovation serves genuine user needs and reaches all populations.

Innovation Frameworks

Policies should establish clear frameworks defining how innovation is fostered, evaluated, and adopted for assistive product and assistive technology systems. Innovation frameworks should identify priority areas for innovation (emerging needs, underserved populations, technologies with potential for significant impact), establish mechanisms for identifying and supporting promising innovations, and define processes for evaluating innovations and deciding which to scale and implement. Importantly, innovation frameworks should ensure that innovation is user-centered, responding to identified user needs rather than being technology-driven; mechanisms should exist for users and persons with disabilities to identify priority innovation areas. Frameworks should include mechanisms to evaluate innovation effectiveness, cost-effectiveness, and real-world impact before system-wide implementation.

Research and Development

Government policies should support a vibrant research and development ecosystem addressing AT innovation priorities. Policies should outline government commitments to research in the area of assistive technology, and the mechanisms for that support, including partnerships, and funding.

AI and Digital Technologies

Artificial intelligence, machine learning, and advanced digital technologies offer significant potential for AT innovation. Policies should create space for responsible AI innovation in AT while establishing safeguards protecting users from harm. Policies should address data governance questions: what data AI systems use, who controls and benefits from data, how user privacy is protected, and how bias in data or algorithms is identified and mitigated. Multilingual support should be an explicit requirement for digital AT, ensuring that products serve linguistically diverse populations rather than privileging English and other majority languages, including the incentivization and funding of development of AT in minority and indigenous languages.

AI policies should address transparency, particularly where AI may be used to contribute to decision making. Policies should include mechanisms for human oversight and override of AI decisions. Policies should require testing of AI systems for bias and discrimination before deployment, recognizing that AI systems can perpetuate or amplify existing inequities. Safety and security standards for AI-enhanced AT should address cybersecurity risks, data breaches, and system failures that could compromise user safety or privacy.

Industry Engagement

Policies should establish transparent mechanisms for industry engagement with clear boundaries and accountability. Policies should encourage industry investment in priority innovation areas through mechanisms such as tax incentives, grants, or procurement commitments, while maintaining regulatory oversight ensuring quality and safety. Public-private partnerships may support innovation while protecting public interest through clear agreements specifying roles, intellectual property arrangements, and benefit-sharing.

Rights Protection and Advocacy

Ensuring that assistive technology is recognized and protected as a human right requires active protection mechanisms enabling users to exercise and defend their rights. Policies should establish clear avenues for addressing violations of rights of access to, or use of assistive technology, support the

capacity of assistive technology users and their organizations to advocate for their rights, and implement measures preventing discrimination against AT users.

Legal Remedies and Complaints Mechanisms

Policies should establish accessible mechanisms enabling AT users to seek remedy when their rights to assistive technology are violated: when they are denied appropriate AT, subjected to excessive delays, charged unaffordable costs, or treated discriminatorily. Complaints mechanisms should be independent from service providers (to ensure impartiality), accessible across geographic locations, and responsive in timely manner. Mechanisms may include ombudsman offices, rights commissions, courts with expertise in human rights, or specialized AT review committees. Complaint processes should be user-friendly, not requiring legal representation or extensive documentation, and should operate in accessible formats and languages. Remedies should address both individual complaints (ensuring the affected person receives appropriate AT) and systemic issues (identifying policy gaps or implementation failures requiring broader change). Legal frameworks should establish liability for AT rights violations, enabling users to seek compensation for harm resulting from rights violations.

Support for Self-Advocacy and User Organizations

Assistive Technology user organizations play critical roles in advocating for rights, monitoring policy implementation, supporting individual members' advocacy, and representing collective interests. Policies should establish mechanisms supporting organizational capacity and sustainability, recognizing that strong user movements are essential to accountability and continued progress. Support may include government funding for operations and activities, tax benefits for organizations, capacity-building support (training in advocacy, policy analysis, organizational management), and mechanisms for AT user organizations to access information and participate in policy processes. Policies should establish formal channels for AT user participation in policy development and implementation (advisory committees, stakeholder consultation processes, co-governance arrangements), ensuring that user organizations have voice and influence in decisions affecting them. Self-advocacy support should help individual AT users develop skills and confidence to advocate for their own needs, access information about their rights, and challenge discrimination or rights violations. Peer support networks should be recognized and resourced as valuable mechanisms for individual and collective advocacy.

Anti-Discrimination Measures

Policies should explicitly prohibit discrimination in AT provision and establish mechanisms for identifying and addressing discrimination. Anti-discrimination provisions should address direct discrimination (explicitly denying AT based on prohibited characteristics) and indirect discrimination (policies or practices that are not explicitly discriminatory but lead disproportionate impact on particular groups). Policies should establish protection against discrimination in employment (accessing AT to perform job duties), education (receiving AT enabling school participation), housing (receiving AT enabling independent living), healthcare (receiving AT-related services), and access to goods and services. Anti-discrimination measures should protect AT users not only from government discrimination but also from discrimination by private service providers and employers. Policies should address the intersection of multiple forms of discrimination, recognizing that persons experiencing multiple marginalization (e.g., women who use AT, ethnic minorities who use AT, LGBTQ+ persons who use AT) face compounded discrimination requiring explicit attention.

Awareness and Information

Policies should establish mechanisms for information platforms which provide accessible, current, comprehensive information about available AT products and services, eligibility criteria, provision pathways, and funding mechanisms, enabling users and families to understand options and navigate systems. Platforms should be multilingual, available in multiple accessible formats (text, audio, video, plain language), and regularly updated. Information should be organized in user-friendly ways enabling people to find relevant information based on their functioning needs, age, context, or other relevant characteristics. Platforms should include information about where to access AT assessment and provision services, how to appeal decisions, and how to access support or advocacy. Platforms should be maintained and updated regularly, with mechanisms for users to provide feedback about information usefulness and gaps.

Emergency Preparedness and Resilience

Inclusive and resilient AT policies must integrate emergency preparedness, ensuring that AT systems and AT users are protected during crises and that humanitarian responses adequately address AT needs. Policies should address the following dimensions:

Continuity of AT Services During Crises

Policies should establish protocols and contingency plans ensuring that essential AT services continue during emergencies. Critical AT services requiring continuity include assessment and fitting (ensuring new users can access AT even during crises), provision of essential AT products (mobility devices, communication aids, sensory aids), repairs and maintenance (preventing loss of AT function when devices malfunction), and user support and training. Contingency plans should identify which services are critical and must continue during different types of emergencies, establish alternative service delivery mechanisms (e.g., remote assessment and provision when in-person services are impossible), pre-position supplies and equipment enabling rapid service restoration, and designate backup staff and facilities. Plans should address continuity of funding and supply chains during economic disruption, ensuring that AT provision is not abandoned when health or social systems are overwhelmed by crisis demands. Policies should require regular testing and updating of continuity plans, learning from actual emergencies to strengthen preparedness. Special attention should be given to vulnerable populations, including persons in remote areas, displaced populations, those in conflict zones, and persons in institutional care, who may lose access to AT entirely during crises without proactive planning.

Assistive Technology in Humanitarian Settings

Humanitarian crises, including displacement, refugee situations, armed conflict, and major disasters create AT needs that often go unrecognized in emergency response.⁽¹²⁾ Persons who use AT prior to the crisis have ongoing AT needs to enable them to survive and maintain basic functioning. Additionally, crises create new AT needs as persons are injured or experience health conditions causing new disabilities. Policies should establish that AT is recognized as essential humanitarian response, and humanitarian response frameworks should include assessment of AT needs among affected populations, procurement and provision of priority AT products, training of humanitarian staff in AT basics, and coordination with national AT systems for longer-term provision. Policies should address the particular challenge of providing AT in displacement settings where normal supply chains and service systems are

disrupted. AT provision should continue as humanitarian crises transition to recovery and reconstruction phases, avoiding abandonment of AT users when emergency response officially ends.

Supply Chain Resilience and Continuity

Policies should establish supply chain resilience through diversified sourcing (not depending entirely on single suppliers or geographic sources), maintenance of strategic reserves of critical assistive products and parts, and agreements with suppliers ensuring priority provision during crises. Policies should encourage regional or international cooperation ensuring that AT supplies can be accessed across borders during emergencies. Just-in-time supply chain models efficient during normal times may create vulnerability during crises, therefore policies should balance efficiency with resilience, and account for specific supply chain continuity needs during a crisis. Data systems tracking AT use and consumption patterns should support anticipatory planning for supply needs.

Communication Strategies

Emergencies require rapid, accurate, accessible communication to the public about safety, resources, and response procedures. AT users who use communication devices, hearing aids, visual information, or other AT to access communication may be left without critical information if emergency communication is not accessible. Policies should establish that emergency communication is provided in multiple accessible formats, including large print, audio, plain language, sign language interpretation, captioning, tactile information, and other formats as needed. Information systems should be tested for accessibility before emergencies occur. Policies should include specific outreach to AT users ensuring they receive emergency information and understand how to access support and services. Communication should address AT-specific information, including where to access repair services, how to obtain replacement AT, where to report AT needs, ensuring that AT users understand how to maintain or restore AT function during crises.

Disaster Risk Reduction Integration

AT users should be included in disaster risk reduction (DRR) planning and implementation, ensuring that DRR strategies protect AT users and that AT needs are addressed in disaster preparedness. Resilient and inclusive policies should require that persons with disabilities and AT users are represented in DRR planning committees and processes, that DRR risk assessments include analysis of specific vulnerabilities of AT users, and that DRR strategies explicitly address how to protect and support these populations. DRR strategies should address how to protect AT users during evacuations, ensure accessibility of emergency shelters and services, and maintain AT function in displacement settings. Community-based DRR approaches should include AT user communities as equal partners. Training for DRR professionals should include understanding of specific needs of AT users.

Monitoring and Evaluation

Inclusive and resilient assistive technology policies require systematic monitoring and evaluation to assess progress toward policy objectives, identify implementation gaps and barriers, understand impacts on AT users and systems, and drive continuous improvement. Policies should establish comprehensive monitoring and evaluation systems addressing multiple dimensions: inputs (resources allocated to AT, funding, workforce, infrastructure), processes (how AT services are delivered, timeliness, accessibility, person-centeredness), outputs (AT services and products provided: number of users served, products distributed), outcomes (changes in AT users' lives, participation, independence, quality of life,

satisfaction), and impact on broader system goals including equity, resilience, and sustainability. Monitoring systems should collect data regularly and systematically from multiple sources, including AT users, service providers, policymakers, health information systems, enabling tracking of trends over time and comparison across geographic regions or population groups. Data should be disaggregated by relevant characteristics (age, gender, ability, geographic location, socioeconomic status, ethnicity) to assess whether services reach all populations equitably or whether disparities persist. Evaluation should be participatory, meaningfully involving AT users in defining evaluation questions, collecting data, interpreting findings, and using results to inform policy improvements. Findings from monitoring and evaluation should be publicly transparent, communicated in accessible formats to diverse audiences, and actively used to drive policy and program refinement, ensuring that evaluation translates into real improvements in AT access and outcomes.

The ARISE Evaluative Tool

Purpose and Scope

The ARISE Evaluative Tool addresses a critical gap in assistive technology policy development and implementation. While many countries have recognized the importance of AT and developed policy statements, few have systematic mechanisms to assess whether their policies comprehensively address essential AT system components or measure progress toward inclusive and resilient AT systems. The Tool enables multiple audiences, including national governments developing new AT policies or strengthening existing ones, advocates and organizations of AT users assessing policy adequacy and identifying advocacy priorities, researchers conducting policy analysis and cross-national comparisons, and service providers understanding how their work aligns with policy frameworks, to evaluate AT policies against international evidence and best practices. The Tool is designed to be adaptable across diverse national contexts, governance structures, economic circumstances, and political systems, while maintaining core commitments to human rights, equity, and resilience.

Structure of the Tool

The ARISE Evaluative Tool is explicitly structured to ensure correspondence between the framework's four core principles (Rights-Based, Participatory, Sustainable, Innovative) and the policy framework components (Conceptualization, Governance and Leadership, Service Delivery, Financing and Affordability, Assistive Technology Workforce, Standards and Quality Assurance, Innovation, Research and Development, Rights Protection and Advocacy, Awareness and Information, Emergency Preparedness and Resilience, Monitoring and Evaluation). The four core principles are embedded throughout the questions which are asked across each of the framework components.

For each of the framework components, a series of questions is asked to address the central concept for the component. The majority of framework components have more than one question. Users will note that questions do not always directly correspond to the subsections of the framework, noting that in some cases, a single question may be asked which addresses concepts more holistically. A section for notes is provided for each of the framework components to provide additional detail regarding the choice of response. This section may also be used to refer to adjacent policies which may be relevant, but are not the subject of evaluation.

Guide for Use

Evaluation can be conducted by any individual or team responsible for AT policy development, implementation, or evaluation, providing an internal assessment of policy comprehensiveness and progress. Evaluation may also be conducted by external evaluators (researchers, consultants, international organizations) providing independent assessment, or through participatory evaluation processes involving multiple stakeholders including government, advocacy organizations, service providers, and AT users. Evaluators should possess understanding of AT systems, policy analysis, disability rights frameworks, and the specific context being evaluated. Policy documents (national AT strategies, legislation, regulations, service standards, financing guidelines) provide primary evidence of what policies establish.

How do we select a policy to evaluate?

The tool may be used in a number of different ways. However, as noted above, the ARISE Framework is designed to apply to a *policy ecosystem*. This may include written legislation, published and unpublished policy programmes and schemes, formal guidance, and organizational policies. While it is possible to use the tool to evaluate a single policy document, it is unlikely that all areas of the Framework (and therefore the evaluative tool) will be considered within a single document.

ARISE focuses primarily on policies and systems governing the provision of assistive technology in a national context, although in countries with federated governing systems, or significant local control over assistive technology provision, this may differ.

Regardless of which policy or set of policies an evaluator or evaluation team choose to review, clear reporting of which policies and/or documents were used for evaluation to ensure transparency, and allow for future comparison if applicable.

How do we prepare to use this tool?

Prior to completing the tool, users may wish to undertake a mapping exercise, collecting key policy documents and reports which have previously been completed.

What expertise is needed to use this tool?

This tool can be used by individuals, however it is more likely that teams who have substantial and thorough knowledge of the policy context will provide a meaningful assessment. When reporting on the use of the tool, clear and transparent information regarding team composition and expertise is important.

How to Score

The evaluative tool uses a scoring system (Box 2) reflecting policy and system maturity across each of the components, typically ranging from 0 (policy component absent) to 5 (comprehensive, well-implemented, evidence-based policy with evaluation of impact or outcomes). Scores should be assigned based on evidence review rather than impression, with clear justification for each score documenting which evidence supports the rating. Lower scores (0-1) indicate that policy components are absent or minimal; these domains represent priority areas for policy development. Mid-range scores (2-3) indicate that policy components exist but lack comprehensiveness, clarity, or implementation capacity; these require strengthening and refinement. Higher scores (4-5) indicate that policies are comprehensive, clearly articulated, and demonstrate potential for effective implementation; these components represent policy strengths to be maintained and potentially expanded. At this time, scores should not be combined into aggregate numbers, as this obscures which specific domains are strong or weak. Instead, analysis should identify patterns (e.g., "governance components are weak while service delivery is relatively strong") informing targeted improvement strategies.

Box 2. Scoring Guide

0 – Absent: Policy component is entirely absent within the policy ecosystem.

1 – Present but Critically Inadequate: Policy component exists only in very limited, ad hoc, or fragmented form with no clear framework or systematic approach.

2 – Minimal or Emerging: Policy component is mentioned or acknowledged in policy documents but lacks detail, clarity, or operationalization.

3 - Developing: Policy component exists and is documented with some clarity, but lacks comprehensiveness or integration across sectors.

4 - Established: Policy component is comprehensive, clearly articulated, and well-integrated across relevant sectors.

5 - Advanced and Evidence-Based: Policy component is comprehensive, evidence-based, and regularly monitored and evaluated.

NA - Not applicable: This component is not applicable to the policy/policies in question.

U – Unknown: The individual or team using the tool does not have the required knowledge or expertise to evaluate this component.

After evaluation completion, results should be analyzed to identify priority areas for policy strengthening. Priorities should be determined through multiple lenses: cross-cutting issues appearing across multiple domains (e.g., weak financing affecting service delivery, workforce, and provision), foundational components that must be addressed before other improvements are possible (e.g., governance structures enabling coordinated action), components with most direct impact on AT user access and outcomes, and components where policy change is feasible given current political context and available resources. Prioritization should be participatory, with AT users having meaningful voice in determining which gaps to address first, ensuring that priorities reflect user-identified needs rather than only government or provider preferences. Action plans should specify concrete policy changes needed, responsible agencies, timelines, resource requirements, and success indicators. Priorities may be phased, with initial focus on high-impact, feasible changes, with additional priorities addressed over time as capacity builds.

Limitations and Caveats

The Tool provides systematic assessment of AT policy comprehensiveness and clarity but has important limitations. The Tool assesses policy on paper and cannot fully capture implementation quality or real-world access outcomes; policies may appear comprehensive but be poorly implemented or fail to reach intended users. The Tool does not measure AT user satisfaction or health/participation outcomes; additional outcome evaluation is needed to assess whether policies translate into improved AT access and user benefit. The Tool is based on international evidence and best practices but may not capture all

culturally-specific or context-specific AT approaches; adaptation to local contexts may be necessary. Evaluation results depend heavily on availability of evidence; in contexts with limited documentation or data systems, evaluation may identify gaps in evidence rather than policy gaps. The Tool cannot account for all barriers to AT access including poverty, geographic isolation, conflict, or political instability that constrain implementation regardless of policy quality. Tool results reflect policy status at point of evaluation; policies are dynamic and require periodic re-evaluation. The Tool is most useful in combination with other assessment approaches including outcome evaluation measuring AT access and user impacts, implementation research understanding barriers to policy implementation, and qualitative research exploring user experiences.

Adaptation Guidance

The evaluative tool is designed to be adaptable across diverse national contexts including countries with different resource and income levels, governance structures, geographic characteristics, and levels of existing AT system development. Countries with well-developed health and social systems may focus evaluation on comprehensiveness and integration of cross-cutting principles (rights-based, participatory, sustainable, innovative) within existing strong infrastructure. Countries with limited existing AT infrastructure may prioritize foundational policy components (governance structures, workforce development) before addressing all framework components. Therefore, adapted tools may focus on essential first steps rather than comprehensive assessment. Federal systems with significant subnational authority may need to evaluate both national policy frameworks and regional/state-level policies, with consideration for the potential that evaluation may reveal policy coordination gaps between levels. Post-conflict or humanitarian settings may emphasize emergency preparedness and resilience components more heavily given the context of immediate need. Rural or geographically dispersed countries may require adapted evaluation addressing AT access in dispersed populations. Adaptation should maintain core commitments to rights-based approaches, equity, user participation, and resilience while allowing flexibility in specific policy components evaluated or emphasis across domains.

Annexes

Annex A. Glossary of Terms

Appropriate Assistive Technology (Appropriate AT): Assistive technology that meets an individual user's needs and environmental conditions, is properly fitted and supported, is safe and durable, and can be obtained, maintained, and serviced affordably within a country, following person-centered assessment and ongoing support.(7)

Assistive Product (AP): Any external product (device, equipment, instrument, or software), especially produced or generally available, the primary purpose of which is to maintain or improve an individual's functioning, independence, and well-being.(6)

Assistive Technology (AT): The application of organized knowledge and skills related to assistive products, including the systems, services, and support structures involved in ensuring access, utilization, and optimal functioning.(6)

Assistive Technology User (AT User): A person who requires or uses assistive technology to enhance functioning, independence, and participation in daily life.

Coordinated Governance Structure: Defined mechanisms and bodies that enable shared responsibility, decision-making, and accountability across multiple sectors or levels of government involved in AT policy, provision, and regulation.

Eligible Population/Eligibility Criteria: The specified group or conditions under which individuals qualify to receive government-supported or insured AT; criteria should be rights-based and non-discriminatory, focusing on functional needs rather than diagnosis or status alone.

Equitable Access: The fair distribution and availability of AT services and products so that all people who need them, regardless of ability, age, gender, geography, socioeconomic status, or other intersecting identities, can obtain and use appropriate AT without undue barriers.

Evidence-Based Policy/Practice: Policy or practice that is informed by systematically collected data, established research findings, and best practice guidelines, ensuring that AT provision achieves desired outcomes.

Framework Component: A primary structural area addressed within the ARISE Policy Framework (e.g., Governance, Service Delivery, Financing, Standards, Workforce), each with specific subcomponents and assessment criteria.

Human Rights-Based Approach: A policy and practice orientation that frames access to AT as a fundamental human right, as articulated in the UNCRPD, ensuring participation, dignity, autonomy, and equality.

Inclusive AT Policy: Policy that ensures that the benefits of assistive technology extend to all eligible individuals, especially those from marginalized or underserved groups, through the elimination of discriminatory barriers and the promotion of user-centered and culturally competent systems.

Interoperability Standards: Technical criteria and protocols that ensure AT products and systems work together seamlessly across manufacturers, platforms, and service environments, supporting user flexibility and integration.

Monitoring and Evaluation (M&E): Systematic processes for tracking the inputs, activities, outputs, outcomes, and impacts of AT policy and service delivery; used to ensure continuous improvement, accountability, and policy adaptation.

Person-Centered Assessment: Comprehensive evaluation that focuses on an individual's functioning, context, preferences, goals, and supports, involving the user and relevant stakeholders as active partners.

Policy (Assistive Technology Policy): A set of measures adopted by governments or organizations to guide the planning, provision, regulation, and evaluation of AT systems, services, and products.

Policy Framework: The structured approach providing principles, essential components, and implementation guidance for inclusive and resilient AT systems.

Provision Model: The methodology by which AT products and services are delivered, including direct public provision, self-directed funding, voucher schemes, resource centers, or hybrid approaches.

Quality Assurance: Processes and standards, often drawing on international or national guidelines, to ensure that AT products, services, and systems meet minimum requirements for safety, effectiveness, usability, durability, and user satisfaction.

Resilient AT Policy/System: An AT policy or system that is equipped to sustain access and service delivery during shocks, emergencies, or disruptions (pandemics, disasters, conflict), and to adapt to changes in context or demand.

Rights Protection and Advocacy Mechanisms: Structures and processes established for users and advocates to seek legal remedies for rights violations, participate in complaints and advocacy, and support user and advocacy organization capacity.

Stakeholder Engagement: Formalized participation of AT users, industry representatives, service providers, and other relevant actors in all stages of AT policy, provision, evaluation, and governance.

Sustainable AT Systems: Systems that maintain capacity for AT service delivery over time, with secure and appropriately allocated funding, robust workforce planning and training, and mechanisms for enduring change and improvement.

User Empowerment: Processes, structures, and education efforts that enable AT users to understand options, participate in decision-making, advocate for their needs, and exercise rights within AT systems and policy processes.

Annex B. ARISE Framework Evaluative Tool

Country:

Policy/Policies Evaluated

Policy Name/Title	Department or Ministry Responsible	Date of Policy

Evaluator:

Date of Evaluation:

Scoring Guide

- 0 - Absent
- 1 - Critically Inadequate
- 2 - Minimal or Emerging
- 3 - Developing
- 4 - Established
- 5 - Advanced and Evidence-Based

Concept	Key Questions	Outcome	Score (0-5)	Source of Evidence	Notes
Conceptualization	Is there a clear and comprehensive definition of assistive technology?	<input type="checkbox"/> Assistive technology is not defined (0) <input type="checkbox"/> Definition is provided, but is vague or not internally consistent (1) <input type="checkbox"/> Definition is provided which is broadly understandable, but is narrow, incomplete, or omits key elements (2) <input type="checkbox"/> Clear definition provided, but somewhat limited in scope or lacks sufficient detail (3) <input type="checkbox"/> Clear and comprehensive definition provided; not fully aligned with international standards (4) <input type="checkbox"/> Clear and comprehensive definition is provided; substantively aligned with international standards (5)			
	Is the definition flexible enough to support the inclusion of emerging technologies?	<input type="checkbox"/> Definition has no scope for emerging technologies (0) <input type="checkbox"/> Very limited or ambiguous wording which could include emerging technologies (1) <input type="checkbox"/> Definition hints at flexibility (e.g., 'including but not limited to') but is tied largely to product lists or categories (2) <input type="checkbox"/> Definition includes forward looking language but does not explicitly include emerging technologies (3) <input type="checkbox"/> Definition is technology-neutral (function/need based) and explicitly allows inclusion of new or evolving technologies without policy change (4) <input type="checkbox"/> Definition is technology-neutral, explicitly future oriented, and supported by criteria used to systematically include emerging technologies (5)			

Governance and Leadership	Is there a coordinated governance structure and approach?	<input type="checkbox"/> No governance structure defined (0) <input type="checkbox"/> Governance structure defined, but not implementable in current ecosystem (1) <input type="checkbox"/> Governance structure defined, limited to a single sector with no cross-sectoral links (2) <input type="checkbox"/> Governance structure defined, limited to a single sector, with some informal cross-sectoral relationships (3) <input type="checkbox"/> Governance structure defined, with cross-sectoral coordination mechanisms and regular functioning (4) <input type="checkbox"/> Mature cross-sectoral governance structure with formal coordination, accountability, and demonstrated impact across sectors (5)			
	Are there mechanisms for stakeholder engagement?	<input type="checkbox"/> No mechanisms for stakeholder engagement (0) <input type="checkbox"/> Limited or tokenistic mechanisms for stakeholder engagement (1) <input type="checkbox"/> Limited mechanisms exist but are ad hoc, poorly publicized, or inaccessible to most stakeholders (2) <input type="checkbox"/> Structured mechanisms for stakeholder engagement with limited support (3) <input type="checkbox"/> Structured mechanisms for stakeholder engagement with resource allocation, and shared decision making (4) <input type="checkbox"/> Structured mechanisms for stakeholder engagement with resource allocation, shared decision making, and formal feedback loops demonstrating impact on policy (5)			

	<p>Is AT recognized as a legal right?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> No recognition of AT as a legal right <input type="checkbox"/> Recognition of AT as a right in text, but entirely symbolic with no enforcement pathway (1) <input type="checkbox"/> Recognition of AT as a right, with limited, inaccessible, or ineffective mechanisms opportunity for rights enforcement (2) <input type="checkbox"/> Recognition of AT as a right with basic enforcement mechanisms (e.g., formal complaints process) but limited reach or success (3) <input type="checkbox"/> Recognition of AT as a right, with mechanisms for rights enforcement that are accessible and show some success (4) <input type="checkbox"/> AT recognized as a legal right with comprehensive, well-resourced enforcement mechanisms and documented precedent demonstrating effective protection (5) 			
	<p>Are there mechanisms for data collection and use to inform policy decisions?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> No mechanisms for AT related data collection (0) <input type="checkbox"/> Limited data collection identified (ad hoc, inconsistent, unusable) (1) <input type="checkbox"/> Sporadic data collection exists but lacks standardization or coverage (2) <input type="checkbox"/> Mechanisms for regular data collection on met/unmet need (3) <input type="checkbox"/> Mechanisms for regular data collection on met/unmet need with some analysis for planning (4) <input type="checkbox"/> Mechanisms for robust data collection and use of data for policy evaluation and development (e.g., dashboards, iterative policy cycles) (5) 			

Service Delivery	Is there a clearly articulated service delivery process including all four steps of the service provision process?	<input type="checkbox"/> No service delivery process identified <input type="checkbox"/> Service delivery process mentioned in limited detail (vague or incomplete outline) (1) <input type="checkbox"/> Service delivery process identified but missing multiple key components (e.g., assessment, training) (2) <input type="checkbox"/> Service delivery process identified, with no guidance (3) <input type="checkbox"/> Comprehensive service delivery process described, covering all four steps with clear guidance (4) <input type="checkbox"/> Comprehensive service delivery process explicitly including all four steps, with standards, training requirements and evidence of application (5)			
	Is there a mechanism for comprehensive, person-centred assessment?	<input type="checkbox"/> No description of assessment (0) <input type="checkbox"/> Assessment is limited and/or not person centred (1) <input type="checkbox"/> Assessment process exists but is narrow in scope (2) <input type="checkbox"/> Assessment is person-centred and needs-based but lacks standardization or coverage (3) <input type="checkbox"/> Person-centred, needs based assessment mandated with clear protocols and trained assessors (4) <input type="checkbox"/> Comprehensive person-centred assessment mechanisms with appropriate tools, training, and quality monitoring (5)			

	<p>Is/are there (a) clearly defined provision model/models?</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> No provision model described</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> One of more provision model identified, with significant limitations (e.g., single sector only) (1)</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Provision model(s) identified but lacking standards (2)</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Provision model(s) identified, with partial standards or incomplete implementation (3)</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Provision model(s) identified, with clear and established standards across contexts (4)</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> One or more provision models identified which provide equitable access to products and services, incorporating user choice and demonstrated outcomes (5)</p>			
	<p>Are eligibility criteria grounded in rights-based, non-discriminatory principles?</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> No eligibility criteria described (0)</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Eligibility is based on diagnostic categories, or restricted by other means (1)</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Eligibility partially need-based but heavily restricted by diagnosis, sector or other discriminatory factors (2)</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Eligibility is based on need, but fragmented across sectors with inconsistent application (3)</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Eligibility is based on need, without minimal discriminatory restrictions (4)</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Eligibility is based on need, without additional discriminatory factors or sector-based fragmentation, with monitoring for equity (5)</p>			
	<p>Are there policies or mechanisms to support repair and maintenance of</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> No mention of repair or maintenance of assistive products (0)</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Repair and maintenance services mentioned but without funding, training, or infrastructure support (1)</p>			

	assistive products?	<input type="checkbox"/> Basic recognition of repair and maintenance needs but limited to ad hoc user-led arrangements (2) <input type="checkbox"/> Repair policies exist with some training and funding, but coverage is inconsistent (3) <input type="checkbox"/> Clear policies supporting repair services, technician training, and spare parts access (4) <input type="checkbox"/> Comprehensive repair ecosystem with standards, funding, training programs, and monitoring of service quality.			
Financing and Affordability	Is there a provision for a national or subnational budget for AT?	<input type="checkbox"/> No provision for national or subnational budget for AT (0) <input type="checkbox"/> Budget mentioned but unfunded or inaccessible (1) <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, allocated in the context of changing government priority (ad hoc or opportunistic) (2) <input type="checkbox"/> Budget allocated with some reference to priority areas but lacking systematic need assessment (3) <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, allocated by data on need with basic monitoring and adjustments (4) <input type="checkbox"/> Ringfenced budget scaled to robust need data, with performance-linked adjustments (5)			
	Does the available funding cover comprehensive AT provision	<input type="checkbox"/> No description of funding scope (0) <input type="checkbox"/> Funding covers cost of assistive product only with no service support (1) <input type="checkbox"/> Funding covers cost of assistive product but services are minimal or ad hoc (2) <input type="checkbox"/> Funding covers cost of assistive product and basic services (e.g., fitting, training) (3) <input type="checkbox"/> Funding covers assistive product, services, and some ongoing costs (4)			

		<input type="checkbox"/> Funding covers cost of assistive product, services, and ongoing costs (e.g., repair, maintenance, consumables, subscriptions) (5)			
	Are there measures to ensure affordability and equity of cost sharing?	<input type="checkbox"/> No measures are described to ensure affordability (0) <input type="checkbox"/> Insurance or reimbursement schemes are available to limited segments only, with major gaps (1) <input type="checkbox"/> Schemes exist for limited population but exclude most potential users (2) <input type="checkbox"/> Insurance or reimbursement schemes are available more broadly but fragmented or inconsistent (3) <input type="checkbox"/> Insurance, reimbursement or co-pay schemes are available to the full population (4) <input type="checkbox"/> Costs are fully covered according to need for the full population, with equity monitoring (5)			
	Are procurement schemes flexible to accommodate user choice?	<input type="checkbox"/> No information is available regarding procurement (0) <input type="checkbox"/> Procurement according to a rigid, limited list of products with no user input (1) <input type="checkbox"/> Procurement follows limited product list but some exceptions possible (2) <input type="checkbox"/> Procurement includes basic mechanisms to accommodate diverse user need (3) <input type="checkbox"/> Procurement schemes flexible with clear user choice protocols (4) <input type="checkbox"/> Procurement fully flexible to user choice, with voucher systems or equivalent (5)			
	Are tax and import structures supportive of	<input type="checkbox"/> No information regarding tax or import duties on assistive products, components, or related services (0)			

	<p>access to assistive technology?</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Tax and import provisions for assistive technology are mentioned but are unclear, inconsistent, or obstructive (1)</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Some limited concessions exist (e.g., exemptions for a few products) but most assistive products and components remain subject to standard high taxes/duties (2)</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Clear provisions exist for reduced taxes or duties on specific categories of assistive products but coverage is partial (3)</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Broad, clearly defined exemptions or reductions apply to most assistive products and key components with mechanisms to support implementation (4)</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Comprehensive, well-implemented tax and import policies systematically favour assistive products and components, with mechanisms for regular review (5)</p>			
	<p>Are there policies using refurbishment/reuse to improve AT affordability and sustainability?</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> No mention of refurbishment, reuse, or recycling to support sustainability (0)</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Refurbishment mentioned but without quality standards or affordability mechanisms (1)</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Basic refurbishment/reuse schemes exist but have limited scale or cost-reduction mechanisms (2)</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Policies promote refurbishment with basic quality guidelines (3)</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Structured refurbishment programs clearly target reduced cost and waste, with standards and quality guidelines (4)</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Refurbishment/reuse policies systematically described across a range of assistive products, with collection of impact data (5)</p>			

Assistive Technology Workforce	Is there a competency framework for AT provision?	<input type="checkbox"/> No competency framework is described (0) <input type="checkbox"/> Competency framework exists but narrow, outdated, or unenforceable (1) <input type="checkbox"/> Profession-based competency framework for limited roles only (2) <input type="checkbox"/> Profession-based framework covering core roles with basic training requirements (3) <input type="checkbox"/> Skill-based competency framework including multiple roles and clear standards (4) <input type="checkbox"/> Skill-based competency framework including a wide range of roles, with assessment and continuous development (5)			
	Is there provision for workforce planning?	<input type="checkbox"/> No information is available regarding workforce planning (0) <input type="checkbox"/> Workforce planning is mentioned but vague, non-specific, or unrelated to AT needs (1) <input type="checkbox"/> Workforce planning mentioned in limited way but not needs-based (e.g., fixed headcount) (2) <input type="checkbox"/> Basic workforce planning with some reference to service volumes but no formal modeling (3) <input type="checkbox"/> Workforce planning informed by needs assessment and demand estimation (4) <input type="checkbox"/> Comprehensive, needs-based workforce planning using modeling of service demand (5)			
Standards and Quality Assurance	Are there regulatory frameworks in place for standards (including safety, interoperability)	<input type="checkbox"/> No information is available regarding standards and quality assurance (0) <input type="checkbox"/> Standards mentioned but vague or unenforceable (1) <input type="checkbox"/> Basic standards referenced without clear processes, or gaps evident (2) <input type="checkbox"/> Standards and quality assurance mechanisms described but processes incomplete (3)			

	and quality assurance?	<input type="checkbox"/> Standards and quality assurance mechanisms are described with clear process in place (4) <input type="checkbox"/> Comprehensive regulatory frameworks for standards (safety, interoperability) with monitoring and enforcement (5)			
Research, Innovation and Technology	Are there mechanisms to support innovation, research, and development?	<input type="checkbox"/> No information is available regarding innovation, research, and development (0) <input type="checkbox"/> Innovation, research, and development are mentioned but vague or unsupported (1) <input type="checkbox"/> Basic references to innovation/R&D without dedicated mechanisms (2) <input type="checkbox"/> Emerging mechanisms for innovation, research (including piloting), and development identified (3) <input type="checkbox"/> Clear mechanisms to support innovation, research and development, including support for research partnerships (4) <input type="checkbox"/> Robust, funded mechanisms for research and innovation, with monitoring and evaluation (5)			
Rights Protection and Advocacy	Are there mechanisms to support AT user organizations?	<input type="checkbox"/> There are no mechanisms mentioned to support AT user organizations (0) <input type="checkbox"/> Policy mentions support for AT user organizations without clear provision of mechanisms (e.g., vague statements, no structures) (1) <input type="checkbox"/> Basic mechanisms exist (occasional consultation or recognition) but lack resources, clarity or implementation (2) <input type="checkbox"/> Clear mechanisms for support are defined (e.g., funding streams or representation rights) but with limited reach or uptake (3)			

		<input type="checkbox"/> Clear, resourced mechanisms for support (e.g., core funding, formal roles in government) with evidence of operation (4) <input type="checkbox"/> Robust mechanisms with sustained funding, decision-making power, capacity-building, feedback mechanisms for AT user organizations (5)			
	Does the policy explicitly prohibit discrimination in AT provision?	<input type="checkbox"/> The policy does not explicitly prohibit discrimination in AT provision <input type="checkbox"/> The policy addresses discrimination in AT provision in a limited way (e.g., general non-discrimination clause with no AT-specific application) (1) <input type="checkbox"/> Basic mention of non-discrimination in AT contexts but without clear scope, procedures, or enforcement (2) <input type="checkbox"/> Policy establishes protection against discrimination in AT provision with initial mechanisms (e.g., complaints process) but limited accessibility (3) <input type="checkbox"/> Clear prohibition of discrimination in AT provision with accessible mechanisms for reporting and addressing violations (4) <input type="checkbox"/> Explicit, comprehensive prohibition with proactive mechanisms, training requirements, monitoring, and mechanisms of enforcement (5)			
Awareness and Information	Is there an information platform to provide information about assistive technology.	<input type="checkbox"/> No information platform is mentioned (0) <input type="checkbox"/> An information platform is mentioned, but lacks detail on resources, responsibility, or feasibility (1) <input type="checkbox"/> Information platform is named but with minimal description of scope, resources, or maintenance (2)			

		<input type="checkbox"/> Platform is described with some assigned responsibility but unclear or inadequate ongoing support (3) <input type="checkbox"/> Platform clearly described with defined responsibility and basic resources for maintenance/feedback (4) <input type="checkbox"/> Fully described platform with sustained resourcing, feedback loops, and mechanisms for evaluation of user reach/impact (5)			
Emergency Preparedness and Resilience	Are there protocols or contingency plans for communicating and delivering AT services during emergencies or humanitarian crises?	<input type="checkbox"/> There is no mention of AT service provision during emergencies or humanitarian crises (0) <input type="checkbox"/> Reference to AT services in emergencies exists but is vague, impractical or lacks actionable detail (1) <input type="checkbox"/> Basic reference to emergency provision with limited detail on scope, roles, or continuity (2) <input type="checkbox"/> Emergency AT protocols described with some detail but lacking full preparedness or critical service prioritization (e.g., supply chain continuity) (3) <input type="checkbox"/> Well-described emergency AT provision including critical services, roles, and basic contingency plans, including supply chain continuity (4) <input type="checkbox"/> Comprehensive, tested contingency plans for AT in crises with clear protocols, prepositioning, and plans for monitoring and evaluation (5)			
Monitoring and Evaluation	Is there a clear and actionable monitoring and evaluation place within the policy?	<input type="checkbox"/> There is no provision in the policy for monitoring and evaluation (0) <input type="checkbox"/> The policy mentions the need for monitoring and evaluation without additional detail (e.g., indicators, timelines, responsibility) (1)			

		<input type="checkbox"/> Basic M&E reference exists but lacks structure, indicators or assigned responsibility (2) <input type="checkbox"/> M&E plan outlined with some indicators and responsibility but limited scope (e.g., includes utilization data but not impact data) (3) <input type="checkbox"/> Clear, actionable M&E plan with defined indicators including both utilization and impact indicators, timelines, and responsible entities (4) <input type="checkbox"/> Comprehensive M&E plan with robust indicators including both utilization and impact indicators, baseline data, regular reporting, and potential for adaptation (5)			
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Annex C. References

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